

INTERFACIAL FRACTURE MECHANICS APPROACH TO THE TENSION DOMINATED INTER-FIBRE FAILURE UNDER BI-DIRECTIONAL LOADS

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SUMMARY

Inter-fibre failure under bi-directional loads is studied. BEM single-fibre models have been performed and their results analysed by means of Interfacial Fracture Mechanics. The conclusions of the numerical analysis agree with the available experimental results contributing to clarify the failure onset.

Keywords: Micromechanics, Interfacial Fracture Mechanics, matrix/inter-fibre failure, debond, bi-directional loads.

INTRODUCTION

The World Wide Failure Exercise [1,2] encouraged the composites community to provide more accurate and robust failure criteria. The improvement of the existing failure criteria and the development of new ones in this field need to be physically based.

The heterogeneous character of fibrous composite materials implies mechanisms of damage that are associated, at least at micromechanical level, with the generation of interface cracks and, thus, with Interfacial Fracture Mechanics.

The particular case of matrix/inter-fibre failure under tension, typically appearing in impact problems and caused by a dominant tension acting transversely to the fibres is directly connected to the appearance and growth of cracks (debonds) at the fibre-matrix interfaces that eventually lead to the macro-failure [3].

The present work studies the evolution of this mechanism of damage under the combined action of the tension nominally responsible for the failure and a compression perpendicular to it. The objective of this research is to evaluate the influence of this second external load in the evolution of the matrix/inter-fibre failure. Several aspects of this problem have already been analysed by the authors in [4].

BEM MODEL

The study has been carried out using a tool [5] based on the BEM [6], which makes it possible to perform the numerical analysis of plane elastic problems considering contact and interface cracks.

Two single-fibre models have been designed aiming to reproduce the main phases of the mechanisms of damage under study, already identified for the unidirectional tensile case in [3]. The first model, Figure 1a, considers the presence of a debond at the fibre-matrix interface that, under the plain strain hypothesis, grows along the interface subjected to $\sigma_{22} = \sigma_0 > 0$ and $\sigma_{33} = -n\sigma_0 < 0$ ($0 \leq n \leq 0$).

Figure 1. Single fibre model considering the presence of a) a crack at the fibre-matrix interface, b) a crack in the matrix.

In order to characterize the problem from the Fracture Mechanics point of view the energy release rate, G , will be used. The expression employed, based on the virtual closure crack technique [7] for a circular crack that propagates from a certain debonding angle, α , Figure 2a, to $\alpha + \Delta\alpha$ ($\Delta\alpha$ being much smaller than the crack length), is:

$$G(\alpha, \Delta\alpha) = \frac{1}{2\Delta\alpha} \int_0^{\Delta\alpha} \{ \sigma_{rr}(\alpha + \theta) \Delta u_r(\alpha - \Delta\alpha + \theta) + \sigma_{r\theta}(\alpha + \theta) \Delta u_\theta(\alpha - \Delta\alpha + \theta) \} d\theta \quad (1)$$

where σ_{rr} and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ represent, respectively, radial and shear stresses along the interface, and Δu_r and Δu_θ the relative displacements of the crack faces. θ is the circumferential coordinate with reference to axis 2. Both modes of fracture, I (associated to σ_{rr}) and II (associated to $\sigma_{r\theta}$), are obviously considered in Equation (1).

When the presence of an incipient crack in the matrix is considered, the previous model is altered to represent the case of a crack that has first grown along the interface and, once kinked into the matrix, is progressing through it, Figure 1b. In this case Equation (1) is appropriately adapted to a crack in a homogeneous material. The materials chosen for the analysis correspond to a typical configuration among fibre reinforced materials: a glass fibre-epoxy matrix system whose elastic properties are listed in Table 1. The fibre radius considered has been $a = 7.5 \cdot 10^{-6} m$.

Dimensionless results for G will be presented in all cases. These dimensionless values are obtained, following [8, 9], by dividing the values of G by $G_0 = \left(\frac{1 + \kappa^m}{8\mu^m} \right) \sigma_0^2 a \pi$, where $\kappa^m = 3 - 4\nu^m$, μ^m is the shear modulus of the matrix and σ_0 denotes the value of the applied tension.

Table 1: Elastic properties of the materials.

Material	Poisson coefficient, ν	Young modulus, E
Matrix (epoxy)	$\nu^m = 0.33$	$E^m = 2.79 \times 10^9$ Pa
Fibre (glass)	$\nu^f = 0.22$	$E^f = 7.08 \times 10^{10}$ Pa

MICROMECHANICAL PHASES OF THE INTER-FIBRE FAILURE UNDER TENSION

The initial phases of the mechanism of damage under unidirectional tension were studied in [3] by means of a single fibre model. The conclusions provided by that study are briefly revised in what follows and summarized in Figure 1.

The results obtained showed that crack nucleation is controlled by the radial stress generated between fibre and matrix, the maximum values being placed at the angles 0° and 180° with respect to the direction normal to the tension applied, Figure 2a. Once a small debonding crack appears (in particular, one of 10° length centred at 0° was assumed in accordance with the range predicted by Mantič [10]), single-fibre BEM models, similar to that shown in Figure 1a just considering the application of σ_{22} , were employed for the characterisation of crack growth.

Figure 2. Micromechanical phases of inter-fibre failure under unidirectional tension.

The results produced by the BEM model, analysed following the energetic approach of Interfacial Fracture Mechanics, predicted an unstable growth of the interface crack up to a position characterized by $\theta_d = 60^\circ - 70^\circ$, Figure 2b. The study also showed that the end of unstable growth coincides with the development of a physically relevant contact zone at the crack tip. The third step of the analysis, Figure 2c, ascertained the condition under which the interface crack would find it easier to kink and to penetrate into the matrix than to continue growing along the interface. The coalescence of these kinked

cracks caused the appearance of a macromechanical failure that, as expected from the experiments [3], was oriented perpendicularly to the external load direction.

DAMAGE INITIATION

The presence of an external compression σ_{33} acting at the same time as σ_{22} could alter the origin of the failure and, thus, the development of the interface crack. The initiation of damage at the interface has been considered in this work to be controlled by the stress state of the undamaged interface as was already done in [3]. Then it is fundamental to analyse the influence that the different levels of σ_{33} have both on σ_{rr} and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ of the undamaged interface. The distribution of σ_{rr} (Figure 3) and $\sigma_{r\theta}$ (Figure 4) have been obtained according to [11]. Three different values of n coefficient have been considered: 0, 0.5 and 1. Based on this the notation employed to distinguish between the different bi-directional cases follows the scheme: T- n C (T=tension, C=compression).

Figure 3. Distribution of σ_{rr} at the undamaged interface versus angular position α for the cases T-0, T-0.5C and T-C.

Curves presented in Figure 3 show that the presence of σ_{33} does not qualitatively alter the distribution of σ_{rr} at the interface. Quantitatively, and with reference to the T-0 case, compressive σ_{rr} significantly increases as σ_{33} does, whereas maximum tensile σ_{rr} increases only slightly. With reference to $\sigma_{r\theta}$, Figure 4, the location of the maxima is not affected by the increasing presence of σ_{33} though their values increase to finally achieving the value of the maximum σ_{rr} for the T-C case. Comparing both figures and taking into account the relative values of the strength of the interface under tension and shear [12], it can be considered that, if the applied σ_{33} is lower than the applied σ_{22} , σ_{rr} will control the initiation of failure. Based on the former reasoning an initial debond at the interface of 10° length centred in axis 2 (position at which σ_{rr} is maximum) will be assumed for the next section.

Figure 4. Distribution of $\sigma_{r,\theta}$ at the undamaged interface versus angular position α for the cases T-0, T-0.5C and T-C.

THE INTERFACE CRACK

Energy Release Rate

Once the presence of a small debond is considered at the interface its evolution is studied by means of the BEM model shown in Figure 1a and its growth evaluated in terms of the Energy Release Rate, G .

Figure 5.a) G of the interface crack for the cases T-0, T-0.25C, T-0.5C and T-C, b) scaled representation.

The results obtained show that the presence of $\sigma_{33} < 0$ does not qualitatively alter the evolution of G versus θ_d , though it is found that its level increases as $\sigma_{33} < 0$ does, which means that the load level required for crack propagation is lower. This fact can be clearly appreciated in Figure 5a where the curves corresponding to T-0, T-0.25C, T-0.5C and T-C are jointly represented. In any case and in order to make comparative growth predictions, it is interesting to scale the evolutions presented in Figure 5a so that

all of them coincide at the initial point. Thus, taking into account that the growth of the first debond will appear in each case for a slightly different external load σ_0 , the curves contained in Figure 5a have been translated to Figure 5b, representing each of them the evolution of the interface crack for a different load level but with the same value of G for the initial debond.

Interface crack propagation

The prediction of growth of the interface crack is made by comparing G with its corresponding critical value, G_c . Considering a G_c evolution in accordance with [13], as was already done in [3] for the T-0 case, this G_c depends on the fracture mixity, ψ_K , in the following way:

$$G_c(\psi_K) = G_{1c} \left(1 + \tan^2(1 - \lambda)\psi_K \right), \quad (2)$$

where G_{1c} is the critical value of G_c for Mode I and λ is the fracture mode sensitivity parameter.

$G - G_c$ comparisons for the cases T-0 and T-C (taken as representative of all T- n C cases) are plotted in Figure 6. A value of 0.2 has been chosen for λ (according to the typical range for the glass-epoxy systems) and G_{1c} has been taken as the value that makes G and G_c coincide for the first debonding angle, $\theta_d = 10^\circ$ in this case. This criterion for the election of G_{1c} can be implemented once the scaled representation of the G curves has been considered.

The results shown in Figure 6 predict an unstable growth of the interface crack that reaches lower debonding angles as the presence of $\sigma_{33} < 0$ increases, though the value of σ_0 needed for the initiation of the crack growth is lower as the presence of σ_{33} increases, which means that the presence of a compression superimposed on the tension nominally responsible for the failure accelerates the failure.

As was mentioned before, the end of the unstable growth of the interface crack is associated in the T-0 case with the development of a physically relevant contact zone at the crack tip. In this sense, it has been checked in this study that the T- n C cases also fulfill this pattern; on the subject, a contact zone of finite size is first detected at $\theta_d = 45^\circ$ for the particular case of T-C and $\lambda = 0.2$, leading, as shown in Figure 6, to an earlier end of the unstable crack growth with respect to the T-0 case. Regarding to this, the possible range of end of unstable growth of the interface crack can be determined by repeating the same analysis presented in Figure 6 for different values of λ covering the typical range for glass-epoxy systems. This complementary analysis has been carried out founding that the end of unstable growth for the T-C case approximately corresponds to the interval $[45^\circ, 65^\circ]$.

Figure 6. G and G_c of the interface crack for the cases T-0 and T-C.

KINKING AND PROPAGATION THROUGH THE MATRIX

The stable position reached by the crack at the interface after a period of unstable propagation warns about the possible occurrence of a different stage in the mechanism of damage under study. Following with the steps already detected for the T-0 case the possibility of kinking towards the matrix is analysed in this Section.

The first step of the kinking analysis consists in the study of the circumferential stress around the interface crack tip in order to identify the preferential direction of kinking, associated to the maximum circumferential stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max}$, for each position of the interface crack, according to the Maximum Circumferential Stress Criterion [14].

The BEM model presented in Figure 1a has been used for this analysis and the distribution of the circumferential stress has been evaluated for interface crack tips corresponding to debonding angles in the range $[30^\circ-90^\circ]$ and 3 different distances, r , to the crack tip $[0.001a, 0.005a, 0.01a]$. The results obtained for the T-C case show that $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max}$ takes place for $\theta_d = 60^\circ$ though this value is also approximately achieved by the maxima associated to $\theta_d = 50^\circ$ and $\theta_d = 70^\circ$.

With reference to the orientations associated to $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max}(\theta_d)$, $\theta(\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max})$, these results are presented in Figure 7 for each θ_d considered. In this Figure it can be observed that the results show a weak dependence on r . The most relevant information provided by this Figure is in any case the fact that $\theta(\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max})$ coincides with the expected macromechanical orientation of failure, 90° , for $\theta_d = 70^\circ$.

Figure 7. $\theta(\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{\max})$ predictions versus θ_d .

Once the preferential kinking direction of the interface crack has been calculated it is necessary to study, in accordance to the procedure followed for the T-0 case [3], the kinking occurrence from an energetic point of view. To this end the BEM model shown in Figure 1b has been used and the presence of a small vertical (perpendicular to the external applied tension, σ_{22}) kinked crack has been considered for different θ_d and subjected to a T-C loading state. G values associated to the different kinked cracks have been calculated and represented in Figure 8 versus θ_d . G evolution of the interface crack for the T-C case, already presented in Figure 5 has been also included in this Figure.

Figure 8. G comparison between the interface crack and vertical kinked cracks.

The results obtained show that for the θ_d range employed in this study, the value of G associated to the kinked crack is greater than the corresponding G value associated to the interface crack. It can also be detected that the maximum differences are found for θ_d corresponding to the range of ending of unstable growth at the interface.

In addition, an energetic evaluation of the later propagation of the crack in the matrix, once kinked, has been carried out. The results are presented in Figure 9 for the particular case of $\theta_d = 70^\circ$, which, following the numerical predictions, has associated an almost exact vertical kinked crack, i.e. perpendicular to the external tension. The increasing tendency shown by G , together with the constant value of G_{II} and the dominance of G_I , leads to the conclusion that, if kinking takes place the later growth of the crack in the matrix is unstable.

Finally, for the bi-material system under study it can be considered that the Mode II critical value of G associated to the interface is greater than the Mode I critical value of G associated to the matrix. Thus, based on the relative values of G_c for the interface and the matrix and the different character of growth for both possibilities: unstable and in Mode I for the matrix, and stable and in Mode II for the interface, favourable conditions are found for the kinking of the interface crack towards the matrix once it has reached a stable position at the interface.

Figure 9. Evolution of G of a vertical kinked crack that grows in the matrix. $\theta_d = 70^\circ$.

CONCLUSIONS

The numerical results obtained for the tension-compression bi-directional cases considered predict the appearance of the same stages in the generation of the damage as those already detected for the mechanism of damage under unidirectional tension. In spite of this, some differences have been found related to the morphology of the crack at the different stages of the mechanisms as well as the loading level required for the progression of the damage. In this sense, the most relevant conclusion provided by the numerical analysis is this one: the presence of a compression superimposed on the tension nominally responsible for the failure accelerates the failure occurrence. Finally, the results of the bi-directional experimental tests, previously carried out by the authors [4], agree with the conclusions derived from the micromechanical numerical study.

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